

Constitutional Problems Concerning Anthraquinonoid Vat Dyes*

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At meetings of the Dyestuffs Exploratory Committee set up by the Govt. of India in 1941 and during discussions between an Indian and a British firm at about the same time, I put forward the somewhat heterodox view that anthraquinonoid vat dyes and azoic components, rather than the direct cotton dyes and Sulphur Black, should be produced in the first phase of a 10 or 15-year plan for a dyestuff industry in India. The proposition was justified by the fact that the cotton textile industry, the largest of all Indian industries, increasingly demanded shades of all-round fastness, which could only be obtained from the anthraquinonoid vat dyes and the azoic dyes. Apart from their technical importance, the anthraquinonoid vat dyes are of interest to the organic chemist because they include many complex homocyclic and heterocyclic compounds and offer numerous problems for investigation from the point of view of structure determination, degradation methods, synthetical reactions, and relationships between chemical constitution and colour, affinity for cellulose, and fastness properties. Simultaneously with attempts to stimulate interest in the production of vat dyes in India, work on a few problems in this vast area was undertaken by a small group in the University of Bombay.

Chromatographic Analysis

Vat dyes are insoluble in water and water-soluble impurities can therefore be readily removed. The nonvattable impurities are also easy to remove by reduction with sodium hydrosulphite in aqueous sodium hydroxide, filtration, and reoxidation by air; but the possibility of permanent chemical changes, such as dehalogenation, reduction of nitro groups, and hydrolysis of amide groups should be borne in mind. The isolation of the main constituent of a commercial vat dye may involve separation from other vat dyes added for shading purposes. Because of the sparing solubility of the anthraquinonoid vat dyes in organic solvents, chromatographic separation has to be carried out at high temperatures, using high-boiling solvents such as *o*-dichlorobenzene, 1,2,4-trichlorobenzene, molten naphthalene, phenol, and cresols. A simple apparatus and procedure for this purpose were described in a recent paper¹. Solutions of the leuco derivatives of vat dyes in aqueous sodium hydroxide are unsuitable for paper chromatography because of their rapid oxidation to the insoluble quinones; but when sodium hydroxide is replaced by aqueous tetraethylenepentamine, $\text{NH}_2(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH})_3\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{NH}_2$, reduction with sodium hydrosulphite yields a clear and very stable vat. The solution can be submitted to paper chromatography or chromatographed on a column of cellulose powder, the same reagents in aqueous solution being employed for developing the chromatogram².

Absorption Spectra of Leuco Derivatives

In connection with the constitution of lac dye constituents it was observed that the spectra of the leuco derivatives in alkaline solution are useful for distinguishing between hydroxynaphthaquinones and hydroxyanthraquinones; the former have an absorption maximum at about 390 $\text{m}\mu$; the latter exhibit a maximum in the 420-450 $\text{m}\mu$ region, together in some cases with a broad diffuse band in the 500 $\text{m}\mu$ region³. The absorption spectra of the leuco derivatives of anthraquinonoid vat dyes in sodium hydroxide solution are of limited value for their characterization. Waters⁴ has stated that in pursuance of a general programme of research on the dyeing of cellulose he carried

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out measurements of the absorption spectra of various vat dyes in both the reduced and oxidised states; but the only dye for which the absorption curves were given was Caledon Yellow 3G (1,5-bisbenzamidoanthraquinone). Waters observed a characteristic similarity in the absorption spectra of the reduced dyes, referring presumably to the benzamidoanthraquinones he examined; there were two distinct absorption bands with maxima in the blue and yellow regions. One difficulty in the determination of the spectra of the leuco derivatives in alkaline solution is their oxidisability, but this is overcome by the addition of ethanol or dioxane. The spectra of the sodium salts of the leuco derivatives of anthraquinone, 1- and 2-aminoanthraquinone, and a series of acylamidoanthraquinones were determined by Padhye *et al.*, who found that the spectrum of anthrahydroquinone did not undergo any characteristic change by the substitution of an amino or a benzamido group in the 1- or 2-position⁵. The spectrum of anthraquinone in the reduced state shows one sharp peak of high intensity at 420 m μ (A band) and a broad diffuse band at about 506 m μ (B band). On the introduction of an amino group in the 1- or 2-position, no major change in the nature of the spectra of the reduced compounds is observed. The oxidised compounds behave very differently, profound changes in the absorption spectra occurring when anthraquinone is substituted by an amino group in the 1- or 2-position. This is understandable if we associate the colour of the aminoanthraquinones with the contribution of low-energy structures, such as (I) and (II), to the excited states of the molecules⁶. In the alkaline solutions of the leuco derivatives of anthraquinone and the aminoanthraquinones, the absorption spectra are those of the anions of anthrahydroquinones. The negatively charged oxygen atoms inhibit the contribution of structures involving positively charged nitrogen, and as a result there is little or no electronic interaction between the amino group and the anthrahydroquinone nucleus as in structures (I) and (II). The amino group will then show presumably an effect like the anilinium ion or the amino group in 2,6-dimethylaniline, because of restricted electron mobility. The A band of leuco anthraquinone is shifted to 430 m μ in leuco 1-aminoanthraquinone; in leuco 2-aminoanthraquinone there is a hypsochromic shift to 418 m μ . The B band of the leuco anthraquinone spectrum at 506 m μ undergoes reverse changes, the 1-amino compound showing a hypsochromic shift and the 2-amino compound a bathochromic shift.

(I)

(II)

The introduction of one or more benzamido groups in the α - or β -position does not effect any change in the nature of the spectrum, except for shifts in the wave lengths of maximum absorption. The spectrum of leuco 1-benzamidoanthraquinone shows that the A band is at about 425 m μ as in the spectrum of leuco 1-aminoanthraquinone, and has the same order of intensity. The B band, which does not show an appreciable shift in the 1-amino compound as compared with anthraquinone, has shifted considerably to the longer wave length side and has a slightly greater intensity than the corresponding band for leuco 1-aminoanthraquinone. The A band of leuco anthraquinone shows a much greater bathochromic shift in the 2-benzamido than in the 1-benzamido derivative, but there is little increase in intensity. There is no distinct B band in the spectrum of leuco 2-benzamidoanthraquinone corresponding to the B band of leuco anthraquinone, although there is a flat absorption in this region which shows the presence of

this band. In leuco 2-benzamidoanthraquinone the A band, which does not show any shift in leuco 2-aminoanthraquinone as compared with leuco anthraquinone, exhibits a considerable shift and has about the same order of intensity. Thus it is principally one of the two bands (A or B) of leuco anthraquinone, which shifts on substitution of an amino group in the 1- or 2-position; on benzoylation the position of this displaced band remains nearly the same, but the second band undergoes a bathochromic shift. Further introduction of a benzamido group in the 4- or 5-position of 1-benzamidoanthraquinone decreases the intensity of absorption, this decrease being considerable in the case of leuco 1,5-bisbenzamidoanthraquinone; the wave lengths of the absorption maxima are also shifted, although not very significantly.

Steric Hindrance in Dibenzanthrnyls and Dibenzanthrones

There are many examples of the effect of steric hindrance to planarity on the absorption spectra of organic molecules. A common effect of such steric hindrance is a reduction in the intensity of maximum absorption, usually, but not invariably, accompanied by a hypsochromic shift in the long wave length absorption. Changes in the absorption spectra as a result of steric hindrance to planarity can be related to its interference with the resonance of the molecule either in the ground state or excited state. Steric hindrance in the excited state decreases the resonance stabilization of that state and increases the transition energy, leading therefore to a hypsochromic shift in the absorption spectrum. On the other hand, steric hindrance in the ground state decreases the energy of transition because of the reduced resonance stabilization of the ground state, and the consequence is a bathochromic shift in the absorption spectrum. In a review of the effects of steric hindrance to planarity of dye molecules, Brooker⁷ has discussed two distinct types of behaviour. Most of the compounds studied were characterized by a single low-energy resonance structure. As a rule the crowding substituent does not affect this single dominant structure, which is usually benzenoid contributing principally to the ground state, but affects other high-energy structures, which contribute mostly to the excited states of the molecule, resulting in a hypsochromic shift of the spectrum. But where the molecule can be represented by two identical structures of low energy, the effect of steric hindrance is to decrease the contribution of these identical structures to the ground state of the molecule, thereby leading to a bathochromic shift.

The effect of steric factors on the absorption spectra of diphenyl derivatives has been thoroughly investigated⁸. When the two benzene rings are forced into different planes as in dimesityl, the absorption corresponds to that of mesitylene ($\epsilon \times 2$). Friedel *et al.* have discussed the effects of steric hindrance on the spectra of the three dinaphthyls and they have shown that the effect of steric hindrance in 1,1'-dinaphthyl results in a spectrum very similar to that of naphthalene, except for the relative absence of fine structure. The spectra of benzanthrone, 3,3'-dibenzanthrnyl (III), and 4,4'-dibenzanthrnyl (IV) are very similar, indicating that in the two latter compounds there is no new chromophoric system, and that there are no possibilities of extended conjugation across the carbon-carbon bond connecting the two benzanthrnyl residues because of the steric hindrance of the hydrogen atoms in the 4,4'- or 3,3'-positions⁹.

(III)

(IV)

The absorption spectrum of 16,17-dimethoxydibenzanthrone (Caledon Jade Green; VI), a dye of outstanding technical importance, in comparison with that of dibenzanthrone (V) was first discussed in connection with the substantivity for cellulose of the leuco derivatives of anthraquinonoid vat dyes in alkaline solution¹⁰. Attention was drawn to the overlap of the van der Waals radii of the methoxyl groups; the bathochromic shift in passing from dibenzanthrone (V) to the 16,17-dimethoxy derivative (VI) was explained by assuming a planar configuration for the two methoxyl groups and the dibenzanthrone system by adjustments in bond lengths and bond angles.

(V)

(VI)

A revised scale drawing of (VI), using bond lengths and bond angles varying within the limits indicated by the actual values for perylene¹¹, shows that a planar configuration is possible in which the overlap of the van der Waals radii of the methoxyl groups is relatively small¹². Further, the van der Waals radii of the ethereal oxygen atoms will be reduced by resonance with the carbonyl groups as shown in (VII). Since the additional energy required for achieving planarity decreases the resonance energy, the energy of the ground state is raised from its normal level and 16,17-dimethoxydibenzanthrone therefore absorbs at longer wave length than dibenzanthrone. The intensity of the long wave length band of 16,17-dimethoxydibenzanthrone is much lower than that of dibenzanthrone because of the lowering of the probability of the transition from the ground state to the excited state in the strained molecule.

(VII)

(VIII)

Durie and Shannon¹³ have determined in chlorobenzene and dioxane solution the electronic absorption spectra of dibenzanthrone (V), 16,17-dimethoxydibenzanthrone (VI), and other dibenzanthrone derivatives. They found that their curves for (V) and (VI) were similar to those presented by Padhye *et al.*⁹, who used *o*-chlorophenol as solvent, and differed considerably in the positions of the peaks as well as the intensities from the data of Moran and Stonehill¹⁴, who determined the absorption spectra in ethanol and chlorobenzene. We have noticed discrepancies between our results and those of Moran and Stonehill for other vat dyes. As suggested by Durie and Shannon, it appears likely that Moran and Stonehill failed to obtain complete solution because of the extremely low solubility of (V) and (VI) in both ethanol and chlorobenzene.

Durie and Shannon considered that the argument concerning the colour of (VI) based on the coplanarity of the methoxyl groups and the polycyclic system was invalidated by the proved non-planarity of molecules such as (VIII). An overcrowded molecule, such as (VIII), in which the repulsion forces between non-bonded carbon atoms situated less than 3.0 Å produce distortions from a planar arrangement as shown in (IX) for 1,2-benzophenanthrene, is, however, very different from (VI) in which the strain is accommodated by a slight deformation in the angles of the bonds linking the ethereal oxygen atoms to the carbon skeleton and by the stretching and compression of bond lengths in the dibenzanthrone system. Because of the single-bond character of the two carbon-carbon bonds uniting the two benzanthrone moieties, Durie and Shannon visualized a twisting of the molecule around an axis of the central ring. This kind of puckering has no parallel in available X-ray data on strained ring systems and is extremely unlikely.

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The ethylene ether of 16,17-dihydroxydibenzanthrone is blue in colour and is a commercial dye (Indanthrene Navy Blue G; C.I. 71200). It is prepared by the action of ethylene dibromide or 2-chloroethyl *p*-toluenesulphonate on 16,17-dihydroxydibenzanthrone. The dimeric structure (X) assigned to it earlier¹⁵ should be replaced by the monomeric structure (XI) in the light of the following considerations. The 16-member heterocyclic ring system in (X) involves no additional strain and the ether linkages should be able to adopt the preferred geometry as in (VI); the ethylene ether should therefore be more or less similar in colour to the dimethyl ether (VI). In the monomeric structure (XI), the lone pair orbitals of the oxygen atoms will be rotated away from the direction perpendicular to the mean molecular plane and participation of the lone pair electrons in the resonance of the aromatic system will be greatly reduced. In (XI) a *cis* configuration is shown for the ethylene bridge, but the more probable *trans* configuration, in which one carbon atom is above and one below the plane of the aromatic framework, will not affect the discussion concerning the monomeric character of the ethylene ether. The ethylene ether therefore will absorb at much shorter wave length than the dimethyl ether and will not be expected to be substantially different in colour from the parent dibenzanthrone. The I.G. prepared polymethylene ethers of 16,17-dihydroxydibenzanthrone and observed that when the methylene groups were increased from 2 in Navy Blue G to 3, 4, and 6, the colour changed progressively to green-blue, blue-green, and dull green¹⁶. If Indanthrene Navy Blue G had the dimeric structure (X), increase in the number of methylene groups should produce little or no alteration in colour; but in the monomeric structure (XI), the strain in the heterocyclic ring will be progressively reduced as the number of methylene groups is increased, and ultimately the ethereal oxygen atoms will be able to take up positions in which they can enter into resonance interaction with the dibenzanthrone system, resulting in a bathochromic shift as in (VI).

(X)

(XI)

The only 5-substituted benzanthrone derivative, to which a reference could be found in the older literature, was 5-nitrobenzanthrone, prepared by Boyes, Grieve, and Rule¹⁷ by a tedious route. 5-Nitrobenzanthrone was subsequently synthesized¹⁸ by taking advantage of the powerful directing influence of the acetamido group in 4-acetamidobenzanthrone; 5-amino-, 5-hydroxy-, and 5-methoxybenzanthrone were then prepared by conventional methods¹⁹. 7,8-Dimethoxydibenzanthrone, which dyed cotton a greenish blue with very good fastness properties, was prepared by alkali fusion of 5-methoxybenzanthrone and also by alkali fusion of 5-hydroxybenzanthrone, followed by methylation.

5,5'-Dinitro-4,4'-dibenzanthronyl was prepared from 4-amino-5-nitrobenzanthrone through 4-iodo-5-nitrobenzanthrone. Reduction with sodium sulphide yielded 5,5'-diamino-4,4'-dibenzanthronyl and reduction with zinc dust in acetic acid, using the conditions under which Vesely²⁰ prepared 1,2-7,8-dibenzocarbazole from 1,1'-dinitro-2,2'-dinaphthyl, gave the carbazole (XII). The carbazole (XII) could not be cyclized to the corresponding dibenzanthrone (XIII), which is the structure assigned by Kunz²¹ to Indanthrene Grey 3B, prepared by the action of hydroxylamine and sulphuric acid on dibenzanthrone (C.I. 59855). By alkali fusion or treatment with sulphuric acid under suitable conditions 4,4'-dibenzanthronyl (IV) can be cyclized to dibenzanthrone; because of the freedom of rotation about the 4,4'-bond, the 3,3'-carbon atoms come close enough for the elimination of two hydrogen atoms with the formation of the stable dibenzanthrone system.

(XII)

(XIII)

Nitration of Dibenzanthrone

Nitration of dibenzanthrone in acetic acid, chloroacetic acid, or nitrobenzene at about 25° gives a mixture of nitrodibenzanthrones, which dye cotton an unlevel green of no practical value. Since the nitro groups are reduced during vatting, the product on the fibre is a mixture of aminodibenzanthrones. When the green dye is oxidized on the fibre with sodium hypochlorite, a deep

black shade is produced, and nitrated dibenzanthrone (C.I. 59850) is marketed under the names of Indanthrene Black BB and BGA, Cibacron Black 2B, Caledon Black NB, etc. Maki²² considered that nitration yielded mainly 16,17-dinitrodibenzanthrone. Ruling out the Maki structure by somewhat equivocal experimental evidence, Bennett, Pritchard, and Simonsen²³ placed the nitro groups in the 3,12-positions by analogy with disubstitution in benzanthrone where the second substituent enters the 9-position, which corresponds to the 3- or 12-position in dibenzanthrone. This orientation was disproved²⁴ by the unambiguous synthesis of 3,12-diaminodibenzanthrone, which dyed a dull green shade turning bright blue after hypochlorite oxidation. The constitution of the essential constituent of nitrated dibenzanthrone has now been conclusively proved to be 16-nitrodibenzanthrone (XIV). Crystalline 16-nitrodibenzanthrone (XIV) was prepared by nitration of dibenzanthrone and also isolated from the commercial product by chromatography on alumina²⁵ at 110°. Chromic acid oxidation, followed by decarboxylation, gave 2,2'-dianthraquinonyl. The constitution was confirmed by reduction to 16-aminodibenzanthrone, synthesized by alkali fusion of an equimolar mixture of benzanthrone and 2-aminobenzanthrone; the resultant mixture of dibenzanthrone, 16-aminodibenzanthrone, and 16,17-diaminodibenzanthrone was separated by hot chromatography. 16,17-Diaminodibenzanthrone was also prepared by alkali fusion of 2-aminobenzanthrone. Oxidation of 16-nitrodibenzanthrone or 16,17-dimethoxydibenzanthrone with chromic and sulphuric acids under controlled conditions gave 1,2,7,8-diphthaloylphenanthraquinone (XV), a new triquinone; further oxidation then yielded the known 2,2'-dianthraquinonyl-1,1'-dicarboxylic acid. Oxidation of 16,17-diaminodibenzanthrone with sodium hypochlorite gave a product which may have the pyridazine structure assigned by Maki to the black dye produced on the fibre by means of Indanthrene Black BB; but it dyed a brown shade, unaffected by chlorine, from a blue vat.

(XIV)

(XV)

The Constitution of Bally's "Benzanthronequinoline" and of Cyananthrene

By the action of glycerol and sulphuric acid on 2-aminoanthraquinone in the absence of an oxidizing agent, Bally (1905) obtained as the major product a "benzanthronequinoline" to which he assigned the structure (XVI). The correct structure was shown many years later to be (XVII) since Bally's compound was identical with the product of the Skraup reaction on 9-aminobenzanthrone²⁶.

(XVI)

(XVII)

Cyananthrene (Cyananthrone; Indanthrene Dark Blue BT; C.I. 68705; Bally and Isler, 1904), prepared by alkali fusion of Bally's benzanthronequinoline (XVII), is no longer used commercially. By analogy with the formation of dibenzanthrone from benzanthrone, but without a re-examination of the preparation and properties of cyananthrene, the structure (XVIII) was assigned to cyananthrene²⁶. Bradley and Sutcliffe²⁷ repeated the preparation of cyananthrene with a slight modification of Bally's conditions and submitted the crude black product to a process of purification, involving extraction with 1,2,4-trichlorobenzene and phenol and hot chromatography of the soluble fraction. A minute amount of a dye was thus isolated, which exhibited in concentrated sulphuric acid solution an absorption spectrum corresponding to an isodibenzanthrone and not to a dibenzanthrone derivative. They then concluded that cyananthrene had the isodibenzanthrone structure (XIX). The presence of (XVIII) in cyananthrene was not excluded by Bradley and Sutcliffe's work, which only provided evidence of the fact that crude cyananthrene contains a substance which probably has the isodibenzanthrone structure (XIX).

The spectrum of the cyananthrene fraction, recorded by Bradley and Sutcliffe, shows the characteristics of dibenzanthrone beyond 780 $m\mu$. Unni²⁸ determined the spectrum of an equimolecular mixture of dibenzanthrone and isodibenzanthrone in sulphuric acid, which indicated that cyananthrene is a mixture of at least two dyes having the dibenzanthrone and the isodibenzanthrone structures. Through the courtesy of Farbenfabriken Bayer an authentic sample of Cyananthrene 0 was obtained and examined. It contained 14% of acetone-soluble substances; chromatography of a benzene solution on alumina led to 4(*N*), 5-pyridinobenzanthrone, 1-azanaphthacene-6,11-dione, 2-aminoanthraquinone, and several unidentified fractions. The residual dye was a mixture of vatable (47%) and unvatable (35%) fractions, neither of which could be crystallized. Both gave similar colour reactions, but the absorption spectra in sulphuric acid were different in the region beyond 770 $m\mu$. The spectrum of the vatable portion showed an absorption maximum at 880 $m\mu$; the spectrum of dibenzanthrone in sulphuric acid has a peak at 848 $m\mu$, while isodibenzanthrone shows no absorption beyond 790 $m\mu$. The available evidence therefore indicates that cyananthrene contains the dipyridino derivatives (XVIII and XIX) of both dibenzanthrone and isodibenzanthrone.

According to Akamatu and Inokuchi²⁹, cyananthrone "has the highest conductivity so far known among the single organic compounds. Its conductivity is almost comparable to that of selenium, which is a typical inorganic semiconductor". The source form which cyananthrone was obtained has not been specified, but the structure (XVIII) is mentioned. "Indanthrene Black", to which Maki's erroneous azine structure is assigned, is also stated to have high conductivity. In view of the interesting semiconductor properties of cyananthrene, attempts are now being made to synthesize the pure dyes with the authentic structures (XVIII) and (XIX). Bradley and Sutcliffe attempted to prepare (XVIII) by the action of copper on the 3-bromo derivative of (XVII), but the only isolable product was the debrominated pyridinobenzanthrone (XVII) or a black insoluble substance, considered to be probably a complex pyridinium salt.

Anthrimides and Carbazoles

When 1,1'-dianthraquinonylamine (1,1'-anthrimide) is heated with aluminium chloride, cyclization to a carbazole takes place; several carbazole derivatives of this type are largely used vat dyes of yellow, orange, khaki, brown, and olive shades. Vigorous treatment with an oxidizing agent, such as sodium hypochlorite, is essential for the development of the pure shade. The mechanism of the reactions has not been fully elucidated and the structures assigned to some of the dyes are plausible, rather than conclusively proved²⁰. An example is Indanthrene Khaki GG (C.I. 71050), prepared by condensing one molecule of 1,4,5,8-tetrachloroanthraquinone with four molecules of 1-aminoanthraquinone and heating the pentanthrimide (XX; AQ=1-anthraquinonyl) with aluminium chloride. The tetracarbazole structure (XXI) is usually assumed, but there has been some doubt if all the four anthrimide groups undergo cyclization. Jayaraman²¹ carried out extensive work on this problem; his results indicate that Khaki GG very probably possesses the tetracarbazole structure (XXI). Jayaraman synthesized and examined a series of anthrimides, corresponding carbazoles, and compounds (such as XXII) containing both anthrimide and carbazole groups. Oxidation and reduction experiments, absorption spectra in organic solvents, and absorption spectra of the leuco derivatives in alkaline solution did not throw any new light on the structure of Khaki GG; the simpler anthrimides and carbazoles could be distinguished on the basis of their absorption spectra in organic solvents, but Khaki GG was almost totally insoluble. The absorption spectra in sulphuric acid supported the tetracarbazole structure (XXI). Anthrimides showed two peaks at about 263 m μ and 360 m μ ; the carbazoles exhibited a peak at about 260 m μ and a broad band at about 508 m μ ; compounds (such as XXII) containing both anthrimide and carbazole groups exhibited absorption bands in all the three regions. Khaki GG in sulphuric acid showed absorption maxima at about 260 m μ and 540 m μ , and the anthrimide peak at 360 m μ was absent. Infrared spectra also supported the tetracarbazole structure (XXI)²². The NH groups in the anthrimides are involved in strong hydrogen bonding with the neighbouring carbonyl groups, and all the anthrimides including anthrimidecarbazoles (XXII) showed two strong bands at 1670-1664 and 1665-1630 cm⁻¹. In the carbonyl region the carbazoles including Khaki GG showed only one band at about 1666 cm⁻¹.

Bradley and Pandit³³ synthesized a compound, which they believed to be the tetracarbazole (XXI), but by a series of reactions which gave amorphous intermediate products and which in fact provided no evidence concerning the structure of their ultimate product. Since their final product dyed a yellowish shade on cotton, it was presumably different from Khaki GG, although this conclusion was not specifically stated.

Cibanone Yellow R and Orange R

By fusing 2-chloromethylanthraquinone or its chloro derivatives with sulphur and treating the product with sodium hypochlorite, a bright orange-yellow dye (Cibanone Yellow R; C.I. 69705; Mayer and Schaarschmidt, 1908) is obtained³⁴. Thionation of the same intermediates at a higher temperature gives Cibanone Orange R (C.I. 69700). Both these dyes were withdrawn from the commercial range of Cibanone colours because of their degradative effect on cellulose when the dyed material was exposed to light. This photochemical activity of Cibanone Yellow R and Orange R is indeed so marked that they have been the dyes of choice for investigating the accelerated oxidation of cellulose by the action of light. Fierz-David and Geering (1935) assigned to Cibanone Yellow R the structure (XXIII) and they regarded Orange R as a polymer related to Yellow R in the same way as Primuline to dehydrothiitoluidine. A re-examination of the chemistry of Cibanone Yellow R and Orange R³⁵ showed the improbability of the Fierz-David structures. It was found that Yellow R, purified by Fierz-David's method, contained anthraflavone (AQCH=CHAQ; AQ=2-anthraquinonyl), and various considerations led to the structure (XXIV) for Yellow R and (XXV) for Orange R.

(XXIII)

(XXV)

More recent work³⁶ has, however, shown that the main tinctorial constituent of Yellow R has the structure (XXVI) and Orange R the structure (XXVII).

(XXVI)

(XXVII)

More intensive hot chromatography of the earlier sample of Yellow R on alumina resulted in the separation of a further quantity of anthraflavone and isolation of a major constituent, analysis

of which fits two methylantraquinone residues per atom of sulphur. Raney nickel desulphurization gave products very similar to those obtained from anthraflavone, and thionation of anthraflavone under appropriate conditions yielded yellow and orange dyes, similar in their properties to Yellow R and Orange R. It was also possible to convert Yellow R by further thionation to Orange R.

Dibenzthiophthene (XXVIII), obtained by Anschutz (1914) in 3% yield by the distillation of *S*-acetylthiosalicylic acid and by Baker³⁷ in 16% yield by heating thiosalicylic acid with phosphorus pentoxide in tetralin, can be prepared in 50% yield by thionation of *o*-chlorobenzyl bromide at 240-80°. Thionation of 1-bromo-2-bromomethylantraquinone (XXIX) yielded an orange dye, very similar in all its properties to pure crystalline Orange R. Condensation of (XXVIII) with phthalic anhydride in a melt of aluminium chloride and sodium chloride, or in acetylene tetrachloride in presence of aluminium chloride followed by cyclization with sulphuric acid, yielded a mixture of products, which contained (XXVII) as well as its isomers. The presence of the linear and other isomers in Orange R and Yellow R as minor constituents cannot be excluded.

(XXVIII)

(XXIX)

In a review of the photochemical degradation of cellulose, dyed with yellow and orange vat dyes, the stability of semiquinone radicals was suggested as an important factor³⁸. The photochemical activity of anthraquinonoid vat dyes has recently been investigated by Bridge³⁹ using flash photolysis⁴⁰. Bridge has found that semiquinone radicals are present and are stable when formed in deoxygenated irradiated solutions, and he has stated that it is not obvious why such stability (observed in the absence of oxygen) should confer activity on a dye. Several other factors undoubtedly have to be considered, and some work on the chemical constitution of the active vat dyes is now in progress. Bridge has arrived at the conclusion that there is no single comprehensive answer to the tendering problem, but that as soon as a full knowledge of the electronic transitions and of the immediate primary products is obtained, a final answer may be found.

Reduction of Quinones to Hydrocarbons

Applications of Raney nickel reduction and desulphurization to thioindigoid and anthraquinonoid vat dyes have been reviewed elsewhere⁴¹. The aromatic polycyclic hydrocarbons and their heterocyclic analogues are of interest for their carcinogenic and other physiological properties, chemical reactivity, electronic structure, and absorption spectra. Since many polycyclic quinones are available as commercial anthraquinonoid vat dyes and others are accessible by known synthetic reactions, it is useful to have a variety of methods for the reduction of polycyclic quinones to the corresponding hydrocarbon derivatives. A well-known general method is the Clar reduction by means of zinc dust, zinc chloride, and sodium chloride⁴². Coffey⁴³ showed that anthraquinone, anthanthrone, and flavanthrone underwent smooth reduction to the corresponding hydrocarbons by treatment with aluminium cyclohexoxide in cyclohexanol. 3,4,9,10-Dibenzopyrene (XXX), a powerful carcinogen, can be prepared from the 5,8-quinone (XXXI) by the Clar reduction, Coffey's application of the Meerwein-Ponndorf reduction, or Raney nickel reduction of the sulphuric ester of the leuco compound.

(XXX)

(XXXI)

Another general method for the reduction of anthraquinone derivatives to anthracene derivatives is treatment with sodium borohydride and boron trifluoride-etherate⁴⁴. The mechanism of this reaction and its limitations are under investigation. In the reduction of anthraquinone, anthracene is accompanied by 9,10-dihydroanthracene, but an overall yield of 70% of anthracene is obtained by aromatization using palladium-charcoal in boiling *p*-cymene⁴⁵.

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